

APPLIANCES COMPONENTS 3D DESIGN SMARTFAN AXIAL IMPELLER DESIGN

SMARTFAN AXIAL IMPELLER DESIGN

The final design of the impeller was determined through a CFD optimization process

Volumetric flow rate increase in order to get a variation of pressure field on the blades

Fluid dynamic efficiency increase

Geometric constraints respect in order to fit in both suggested technologies

STEP 1
1st VIRTUAL PROTOTYPE

Base point for the optimization process

STEP 2
2nd VIRTUAL PROTOTYPE

7 blades (instead of 9)

STEP 3
3rd VIRTUAL PROTOTYPE

Different blade angles

FINAL DESIGN

Different blade chord and different external diameter

Axial impellers characteristics					
	PROTO 1	PROTO 2	PROTO 3	FINAL	
D int	44	44	40	47	mm
D ext	135	135	135	114	mm
thickness	25	25	25	17	mm
blades nr	9	7	7	7	

Optimization steps

STEP 1

STEP 2

STEP 2

STEP 3

STEP 3

FINAL DESIGN

Goal of this step of the optimization process is the evaluation of how an increase of volumetric flow rate affects the pressure field on the blades surface. It was decided to increase the volumetric flow rate by reducing the number of blades

Goal of this step is the obtaining an increase of the maximum FDE value. The shape of the blades was determined using the Euler's law for axial impeller:

$$\text{specific work} = \frac{c_1^2 - c_2^2}{2} + \frac{w_2^2 - w_1^2}{2} \left[\frac{J}{kg} \right]$$

In order to adapt the impeller geometry to both proposed applications, another step was necessary

Every virtual prototype performance is evaluated through a CFD simulation. Main steps of CFD simulation are reported

STEP 1: 3D geometry design

STEP 2: mesh generation

STEP 3: physical setup and calculation settings

SETUP		
STATIC PART	Fluid	ideal air at 25°C
	Reference pressure	1 atm
	Inlet	0 Pa
	Outlet	variable mass flow
	Quiet room	free slip walls
	Real walls	no slip walls
	Turbulence model	Shear Stress Transport
ROTATING PART	Fluid	ideal air at 25°C
	Reference pressure	1 atm
	Angular speed	2400 rpm
	Real walls	no slip walls
	Turbulence model	Shear Stress Transport
INTERFACE	Models	General connection/ Frozen Rotor
CALCULATION	Analysis type	Steady state
	Iterations	3000
	RMS	10 ⁻⁷

Although the final axial impeller (yellow curves) does not show the maximum values of pressure and volumetric flow rate, it guarantees the **maximum value of the fluid dynamic efficiency (FDE BEP)** and the **respect of all geometric constraints**

	P max [Pa]	Q max [m³/h]	FDE BEP [%]
1st prototype	40	140	5,3
2nd prototype	39	160	5,1
3rd prototype	42	190	11,3
final design	20	150	14,3

Performance recap

SMARTFAN IMPELLER DESIGN: PRESSURE FIELDS

During the optimization process the pressure field on blades was monitored

1st PROTOTYPE

2nd PROTOTYPE

3rd PROTOTYPE

P max on blades:
87 Pa

FINAL DESIGN

- Aim of the optimization process was to obtain maximum values of fluid dynamic efficiency (FDE_{BEP}) and pressure on blades, compatibly with geometric constraint
- Pressure field on final design of the axial impeller results to be the most uniform (compared with previous prototypes)

D ext [mm]	blades nr	P max [Pa]	Q max [m ³ /h]	FDE BEP [%]
135				
1st prototype	9	40	140	5,3
2nd prototype	7	39	160	5,1
3rd prototype	7	42	190	11,3
114				
final design	7	20	150	14,3

Pressure field on blades

CONCLUSION